

Comparative cytology of brown planthopper populations infesting *Leersia hexandra* Swartz and rice in the Philippines

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A brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) population was observed thriving on a weed grass, *L. hexandra*, growing on the IRRI experimental farm. The BPH population was unique in its strong specificity for the weed host. Individuals died when caged on rice *Oryza sativa* L. plants.

Morphological and morphometric evaluation of rostral, leg, and antennal characters of grass-infesting individuals

Table 1. Cytological variations in BPH populations infesting rice and grass hosts, IRRI, 1982-83.

Character	Grass-infesting BPH			Rice-infesting BPH			Difference ^a	
	n	\bar{x}	SEM	n	\bar{x}	SEM		
Meiotic cells (no.)	15	81	13.8	15	241	14.5	-160	**
Nonmeiotic cells (no.)	15	89	13.4	15	193	52.7	-104	ns
Meiotic index	15	0.489	0.0365	15	0.651	0.0517	-	0.162*
Interphase nuclei								
Length (μ)	20	9.7	0.22	20	9.4	0.15	0.3	ns
Width (μ)	20	7.6	0.28	20	6.8	0.25	0.6	*
Leptotene nuclei								
Length (μ)	15	38.2	1.39	15	20.1	1.14	18.1	**
Width (μ)	15	30.6	1.08	15	14.3	0.86	16.3	**
Anaphase I clumps								
Pole A length (μ)	11	11.1	0.89	11	9.8	0.31	1.3	ns
Pole A width (μ)	11	4.9	0.57	11	4.2	0.33	0.1	ns
Pole B length (μ)	11	10.3	0.66	11	9.0	0.43	1.3	ns
Pole B width (μ)	11	4.7	0.59	11	4.6	0.24	0.1	ns
Telophase I clumps								
Pole A length (μ)	15	7.7	0.39	14	6.1	0.41	1.6	**
Pole A width (μ)	15	4.8	0.34	14	4.3	0.29	0.5	ns
Pole B length (μ)	15	7.7	0.41	14	6.1	0.35	1.6	**
Pole B width (μ)	15	5.0	0.30	14	4.3	0.32	0.7	ns
Sperm length (μ)	25	25.1	0.56	25	12.9	0.22	12.2	**

^ans = no significant difference, * = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level.

1. Karyotype (1500 X) and idiogram (mm) of rice-infesting *N. lugens*, IRRI, 1982-83.

2. Karyotype (1500 X) and idiogram (mm) of grass-infesting *N. lugens*, IRRI, 1982-83.

indicated that the population was significantly different from populations of biotypes 1, 2, and 3. We categorized the grass-infesting population as a primitive, non-virulent *N. lugens* biotype. To further ascertain its taxonomic status, we studied its cytology and compared it with that of the field population of rice-infesting BPH.

The testicular cells of brachypters sampled from grass and rice hosts were examined using the standard cytological techniques for planthoppers (Table 1).

The two BPH populations differed significantly in frequency of actively dividing cells or meiocytes, meiotic index, width of interphase nuclei, length and width of leptotene nuclei, lengths of telophase I clumps, and sperm lengths, but not in other cellular features (Table 1). Male rice BPH undergo more frequent meioses and yield more but shorter spermatozoa than the male of the grass-infesting BPH.

Substantial variation between BPH populations was observed during the pachytene stage (Table 2). Karyotypes and idiograms of the two BPH populations show clear individual chromosomes of different relative mean lengths (rml) (Fig. 1, 2). For instance, the chromosome with the nucleolus organizing region (site of ribosomal RNA synthesis) measured 47.20 μ m for the rice BPH vs 20.75 μ m for the grass-infesting BPH. The rice BPH generally had longer chromosomes (rml 20.40 to 63.30 μ m) than the grass-infesting BPH (rml 10.25 to 40.75 μ m). The nucleolar organelle of the rice BPH was either a darkly stained body or two fused nucleoli, whereas that of the grass-infesting BPH was simply a densely stained ovoid body.

Chromosomal behavior was similar for both populations, except that the intensive coiling of the rice BPH chromosomes during diakinesis resulted in shorter and more highly heterochromatic chromosomes than those of the grass-infesting

Table 2. Variations in the mean relative lengths of pachytene chromosomes of BPH populations infesting rice and grass hosts, IRRI, 1982-83.

Autosome no.	Mean relative length (mm) of pachytene chromosomes				Difference ^a
	Grass-infesting BPH		Rice-infesting BPH		
	\bar{x}	SEM	\bar{x}	SEM	
1	10.0	0.00	18.0	1.61	- 8.0**
2	10.3	0.21	22.3	1.26	-12.0**
3	10.4	0.27	25.3	1.17	-14.9**
4	10.4	0.27	28.2	1.89	-17.8**
5	11.0	0.36	29.5	1.56	-18.5**
6	20.0	0.00	30.7	1.43	-10.7**
7	20.3	0.21	32.7	1.84	-12.4**
8	20.5	0.22	35.3	0.80	-14.8**
9	21.0	0.06	38.4	1.87	-17.4**
10	30.0	0.00	40.3	1.82	-10.3**
11	30.0	0.00	42.7	1.71	-12.7**
12	30.2	0.17	47.5	2.20	-17.3**
13	30.8	0.17	51.2	2.33	-20.4**
14	40.0	0.00	54.5	2.79	-14.5**
15	40.7	0.21	64.2	2.31	-23.5**

^a ** = significant at 1% level, av of 6 samples.

Table 3. Variations in the means of absolute chromosome length during diakinesis of BPH populations infesting rice and grass hosts, IRRI, 1982-83.

Autosome no.	Absolute chromosome length (μ)				Difference ^a
	Grass-infesting BPH		Rice-infesting BPH		
	\bar{x}	SEM	\bar{x}	SEM	
1	1.6	0.13	1.4	0.07	0.2ns
2	1.9	0.18	1.6	0.07	0.3ns
3	2.1	0.18	1.8	0.06	0.3ns
4	2.3	0.15	2.0	0.00	0.3**
5	2.5	0.17	2.1	0.05	0.4ns
6	2.8	0.17	2.3	0.08	0.5*
7	3.0	0.18	2.4	0.10	0.6*
8	3.2	0.19	2.7	0.08	0.5*
9	3.4	0.20	2.8	0.09	0.6*
10	3.7	0.18	3.0	0.10	0.7**
11	3.9	0.18	3.4	0.12	0.5*
12	4.4	0.23	3.5	0.13	0.9**
13	4.8	0.25	3.7	0.08	1.1**
14	5.4	0.28	4.2	0.12	1.2**
Sex chromosomes	3.8	0.12	3.1	0.15	0.7**

^a ns = no significant difference, * = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level, av of 15 samples.

BPH (Table 3).

Those cytological criteria may be used as complementary taxonomic indices for characterizing and differentiating grass-infesting BPH from rice BPH. These observations further confirm the uniqueness of the grass-infesting population and justifi-

fy its categorization as an additional *N. lugens* variant or biotype. Thus, despite their taxonomic similarities, a distinct cytological incongruity and a certain degree of genetic isolation between the two *N. lugens* populations can be inferred. □

Efficacy of nursery protection and seedling root dip for gall midge control

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In Goa, gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* is a serious insect problem, especially in kharif. We attempted to develop an inexpensive control.

In 1981 kharif, we used susceptible Jaya to test eight treatments: a) carbo-

furan alone (1.25 kg ai/ha), b) 500 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, c) 1,000 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, d) 1,500 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, e) 2,000 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, f) treatment a + chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip